

The early transplanted crop matured on 23 Sep. It was exposed to high temperatures and heavy dew formation during late development and at harvest, which caused more sun cracks and poor head recovery percentage. PR106 had 4-

15% higher head yield (Fig. 2) under different treatments than Jaya and PR103. Head yield was significantly higher with parboil milling than with raw milling. Our findings suggest that

proper manipulation of preharvest and postharvest agronomic practices can ensure greater head rice recovery without requiring additional economic liability. *ℒ*

Effect of levels and modified forms of urea and ammonium chloride on lowland rice

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We studied the effect of levels and forms of urea and ammonium chloride on lowland rice yield in a 1983 field experiment. Co 37 was planted in kharif and IR20 in rabi. Soil was a clay loam. In kharif it contained 225-19.1-470 kg available NPK/ha, with pH 8.2 and EC 0.3 mmho/cm. In rabi it contained 201-18.9-515 kg available NPK with pH 8.2 and EC 0.25 mmho/cm.

Treatments included three forms each urea and ammonium chloride: supergranules, granulated compost, and prilled. N was applied at 0.40, 80, or 120 kg/ha. Ammonium chloride supergranules were made locally with a hand-operated granulizer. Granulated compost was made by mixing urea or ammonium chloride with farmyard manure using a fishmeal pelletizer.

Prilled urea and ammonium chloride were applied in equal splits at last

Yield and yield components as influenced by levels and modified forms of N fertilizer, Coimbatore, India.

N source and level (kg/ha)	Kharif (Jun-Sep)			Rabi (Oct-Feb)		
	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Ammonium chloride</i>						
Prilled	421	85	4.3	435	83	3.7
Granulated compost	421	84	3.9	435	82	3.6
Supergranules	438	87	4.8	458	86	4.2
<i>Urea</i>						
Prilled	421	84	4.3	436	83	3.7
Granulated compost	421	84	3.9	435	82	3.6
Supergranules	438	87	4.8	459	86	4.2
CD 5%	11	0	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.1
<i>Levels of N</i>						
40	345	80	3.1	318	79	2.7
80	406	82	4.2	435	82	3.7
120	458	86	4.6	411	86	4.3
CD 5%	485	92	5.5	488	87	4.8
CD 5%	8	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.3	0.1

puddling and maximum tillering. Supergranules and granulated compost were placed at 5-cm depth 10 d after transplanting. PK at 26 and 48 kg/ha was applied as superphosphate and muriate of potash at last puddling. PK content of farmyard manure was considered in the granulated compost treatments.

Applying 120 kg N/ha in any form gave significantly higher yields than other N levels. Urea and ammonium chloride performed equally well, and supergranules performed better than granulated compost, perhaps because the compost took longer to decompose and release N to the crop (see table). *ℒ*

Efficiency of different nitrogen fertilizers on rice

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We studied the efficiency of different N fertilizers on rice in 1980 wet season (Jul-Oct). Pusa 33 was planted on a lateritic sandy clay loam with pH 5.4, 0.380% organic C, CEC 8.70 meq/100 g soil, 0.041% total N, 4 ppm available P, and 0.048% total K. A no-N control and three sources of N were applied at three levels (see table). All plots received 26-50

Influence of different N sources and levels on rice grain yield, Kharagpur, India.

N (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)					Mean
	Control (no N)	Urea at planting	Urea in 3 splits	Urea supergranule (1-g size)	Sulfur-coated urea	
40		2.8	2.8	3.4	2.6	2.9
80		3.3	3.5	3.8	3.5	3.5
120		3.7	4.3	4.4	4.2	4.1
Mean	2.3	3.3	3.5	3.9	3.4	

LSD (P = 0.05)
 For sources including control 0.25
 For N level 0.14
 For two sources means for the same level 0.34
 For two levels means for the same source 0.29

kg PK/ha at transplanting. The experiment was in a split-plot design

with four replications with N sources in main plot and N levels in subplots.

Urea supergranules (USG) produced significantly higher yields (3.9 t/ha) than the other N sources (see table). Yields with split-applied urea and sulfur-coated

urea were similar, and significantly higher than with urea at transplanting. Yields varied from 2.3 to 4.4 t/ha. USG

performed best at 40 kg N/ha, but at higher N levels was as effective as split-applied urea and sulfur-coated urea. *ℒ*

Residual effect of three N sources and application rates on irrigated lowland rices

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Much of the available information on residual effects of N fertilizers is from studies conducted on upland or nonsubmerged soils. N fertilizer behavior in lowland or submerged conditions is distinctly different.

We studied the residual effects of N on irrigated wetland rice in an experiment after the International Network on Soil Fertility and Fertilizer Evaluation for Rice (INSFFER) trial. Soil was a plinthic Vertic Tropaquept, fine clayey, nonacid, and isohyperthermic at Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia. IR30 was planted. Treatments of the previous experiment are in the table.

During vegetative growth, there were no distinct visual differences among the treatments. Grain yield, panicles/m², percent filled grains, 100-grain weight,

Grain yield, yield components, and soil pH as affected by residual N from 3 sources at 3 rates on irrigated lowland rice, Maros, Indonesia.

N rate (kg/ha)	Previous treatment ^a		Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers/m ²	Filled grain (%)	100 grain wt (g)	Height (cm)	soil pH at harvest
	Source	Method						
29	Control		3.7	248	90	2.0	72	5.8
	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.5	216	91	2.0	67	5.9
	SCU	BI, AP	3.8	237	90	2.0	70	5.9
29	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.8	255	90	2.0	71	5.9
	U	2/3 AP, 1/3PI	4.3	263	91	2.0	72	5.9
	SCU	BI, AP	3.6	254	92	2.0	71	5.9
58	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.3	235	90	1.9	68	6.0
	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.9	262	91	1.9	70	5.8
	SCU	BI, AP	4.2	263	92	2.0	75	5.9
87	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.6	226	91	2.0	69	5.9
	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.6	228	90	1.9	71	6.0
	SCU	BI, AP	4.3	249	91	2.0	75	5.9
116	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.8	258	91	2.0	74	5.9
	Test of significance		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
	CV (%)		16.2	12.6	10.8	8.6	12.0	10.0

^a U = urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, USG = urea supergranule, AP = at planting, PI = panicle initiation, and BI = broadcast and incorporated.

plant height at harvest, and soil pH at harvest indicated no significant differences among the treatments (see table). Even at the highest application

rate (116 kg N/ha), urea, sulfur-coated urea, and urea supergranules had no carry-over effect on the following rice crop. *ℒ*

A simple solution to sulfur deficiency, and an extension technique

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In Apr 1983, a farmer leader from a barrio near MORIF came to the Institute with a problem. He had applied 2 bags of urea/ha 10 d earlier but plants had remained yellow and stunted.

We visited the field and identified S deficiency as the problem. Instead of telling the farmer to apply ammonium sulfate, we established a simple

Mean results of a simple experiment to solve sulfur deficiency in a farmer's field, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Parameter	Control	Urea	Ammonium sulfate	Urea + S	LSD (%)
Dry wt (g/5 hills) 30 d after fertilizer application	78	83	265	257	46
Plant ht (cm) at harvest	58	62	76	74	10
Panicles (no./m ²)	214	270	388	350	78
Spikelets (no./panicle)	92	102	116	108	ns
Filled grains (%)	84	85	86	86	ns
Grain weight (g/1000)	21	21	22	21	ns
Grain yield (t/ha), 14% moisture	2.5	3.0	5.0	4.8	0.85
Straw yield (t/ha), sun-dried	3.1	3.4	4.9	4.9	0.78
Maturity (days from planting to harvesting)	98	98	90	90	